

**EVALUATE PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS, IN VITRO
ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTI ARTHRITIS OSTEOARTHRITIS
ACTIVITIES OF LEAVES OF *DRYPETES GOSSWEILERI***

**Dr. Arvind Jowar*, Dr. Priyanka Dubey¹, Amol Kumar², Preeti Choudhary³, Timesh
Maskare⁴**

*Akhil Bharti College of Pharmacy, Bhopal, India.

¹Radharaman Institute of Pharmaceutical Science.

Article Received on 29 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 19 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 01 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18811556>

***Corresponding Author**

Dr. Arvind Jowar

Akhil Bharti College of Pharmacy,
Bhopal, India.

How To Cite This Article: Dr. Arvind Jowar*,
Dr. Priyanka Dubey¹, Amol Kumar², Preeti
Choudhary³, Timesh Maskare⁴. (2026). Evaluate
Phytochemical Constituents, In Vitro
Antioxidant and Anti Arthritis Osteoarthritis
Activities of Leaves of *Drypetes Gossweileri*.
World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical
Sciences, 15(3), 763–790.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to evaluate phytochemical constituents, in vitro antioxidant and anti arthritis activities of leaves of *Drypetesgossweileri* (*D. Euphorbiaceae*) collected from Bhopal region of Madhya Pradesh. For plant *Drypetesgossweileri* the same pattern seems to be followed as the Ethanolic extract contain enhanced amount of total Phenol & total Flavonoid. The total phenol content was 0.48mg/100mg while total Flavonoid content was 0.65mg/100mg. Since IC50 and anti-radical activity are inversely correlated, the lower the IC50, the greater the antioxidant activity Thus, quantity of phenol & Flavonoid appears to be maximum for plant in contrast with *Drypetesgossweileri*. In case Ethanolic extract of *Drypetesgossweileri* the IC50 value was found to be 105.18 suggesting that antioxidant capability of *Drypetesgossweileri*. In the current study, complete Freund's adjuvant induced

arthritis in rats were selected to induce arthritis model, because it is the best and most widely employed empirical model for arthritis with clinical and laboratory features such as chronic swelling in multiple joints due to accumulation of inflammatory cells, erosion of joint cartilage and bone destruction and it has close similarities to human rheumatoid diseases Paw swelling is one of the major factors in assessing the degree of inflammation and therapeutic efficacy of the drugs (Begum and Sadique, 1988). Here, a dose of 100 and 200 mg/kg of

Drypetes Gossweileri (0.65 ± 0.035 ; 0.55 ± 0.040) compared to control group up to 28 days, respectively. The experimental model of poly arthritis induced by CFA on rat is widely used for preclinical testing of numerous anti-arthritic agents. *Drypetes Gossweileri* extracts suppressed the swelling of paws in both arthritis models. As a result of inflammatory cells accumulating, joint cartilage erosion and bone destruction, rats were selected for the current study to induce arthritis. It may be because Complete Freund's Adjuvant suppresses the inflammatory mediator released during induction. *Drypetes Gossweileri* The effect of extract *Drypetes* were determined after administration at two dose level (100 and 200 mg/kg b.w.) in arthritis-induced rats. From the results, it may be concluded that *Drypetes Gossweileri* show a significant anti-arthritic effect may be due to the effect of antioxidants like Flavonoid, phenols and saponins present in the plant. As a result of the present study, all of these biological activities have been found to be promising. These contributions can be used as parameters for the authentication of plants or for the development of newer drugs based on their activity. Several therapeutic advantages of an herbal drug are evident in the present study, and it is likely that it will be a potent anti-arthritis agent as well.

KEYWORDS: *Drypetes Gossweileri*, *Vitro Antioxidant* phytochemical, Anti arthritis & Osteoarthritis Activities.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA)

The autoimmune disease rheumatoid arthritis (RA), which is characterized by the destruction of cartilage and bone, is a chronic, inflammatory condition. Statistics show that people with RA make up roughly 0.1% of the world's population. The prevalence of RA is higher in patients who are over 50 and predominately female. Numerous variables influence RA, which is primarily characterized by synovitis. Retrospective investigations on the pathogenesis of RA revealed strong inducers of RA to be both hereditary and environmental variables (such as smoking, obesity, and infections) (Croia *et al.*, 2019). In order to treat RA, a wide range of anti-RA medications, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicines (NSAIDs) and disease-modifying agents, have been created based on RA pathogenesis.

Mechanisms of orthodox treatments

The clinical goal of RA treatment is to reduce pain and inflammation in patients, and further prevent cartilage damage and joint deformity. It is divided into first-line treatment and second-line treatment. The main goal of first-line treatment is to reduce pain and

inflammation. The clinical medication is NSAIDs and glucocorticoid. Although Ibuprofen and Aspirin in NSAIDs could not affect the development of RA, they could quickly reduce the inflammation in patients and relieve their pain to a certain extent. The mechanism of NSAIDs is mainly through inhibiting the production of prostaglandins, thereby inhibiting the inflammatory response (Bindu *et al.*, 2020). At the same time, the anti-RA effect of glucocorticoid was confirmed and studies indicated that its mechanism was related to the inhibition of IL-6 levels. However, continuous medication could lead to cartilage degradation and osteoporosis.

Targeting DCs in the treatment of RA

The strongest antigen-presenting capability and phagocyte characteristics are found in dendritic cells (DCs), which primarily exist in immature phases. Immature DCs developed into mature DCs after being exposed to antigens and outside stimuli. The immune system was triggered as DCs moved from peripheral tissues to stimulated lymphoid organs and transmitted antigens to T cell areas of secondary lymphoid organs (Wehr *et al.*, 2019). The main methods of DC-targeting in RA involve inhibiting DC maturation and migration.

Regulation of fibroblast-like synoviocytes

The main cells involved in the beginning and development of RA are fibroblast-like synoviocytes (FLSs). In FLSs, joint homeostasis can be preserved under typical conditions. But the development of RA might cause excessive FLS migration and proliferation (Bustamante *et al.*, 2017). Joint destruction is brought on by FLS proliferation, migration, and invasion of bone and cartilage. According to reports, RA development may contribute to an imbalance in FLSs cell apoptosis.

Multiple targets interaction

Over the years, anti-RA mechanisms of THMs have been proven to arise from not only single-target interaction but also via multiple target interaction. The inflammatory site of RA is mainly in the symposium. A large number of inflammatory cells infiltrate into the symposium and produce a variety of inflammatory mediators, which aggravate the hypoxia state of the synovial cavity, continuously increase the level of ROS and produce oxidative stress.

Regulation of osteoclasts

RA is considered as arthralgia syndrome in Chinese medicine (Xu *et al.*, 2016). According to TCM theory, its etiologic is due to deficiency of RA patients. At the same time, the patients were attacked by wind cold and other external pathogens, causing joint meridian occlusion and wind cold dampness, eventually leading to fatigue injury.

Current and future status of Indian herbal medicines

India has a wealth of documented and well-utilized traditional herbal medical knowledge. India, with its more than 45,000 plant species, is one of the 12 mega centres of biodiversity. With 16 diverse agro-climatic zones, 10 vegetative zones, and 15 biotic provinces, it has an unrivalled diversity. Thirty million microorganisms, 23,000 fungus, 2500 algae, 1600 lichens, and 15,000–18,000 flowering plants are found in the nation. The WHO recently described traditional medicine (which includes herbal medications) as consisting of therapeutic techniques that were in use before the invention and dissemination of modern medicine and are still in use today, frequently for hundreds of years. Traditional medicine is a culmination of generations of indigenous system of medicine practitioners' therapeutic experiences. Traditional remedies include organic material, minerals, and medicinal plants. Only traditional medications that use medicinal plant preparations as their main therapeutic component are classified as herbal pharmaceuticals. Their use is first documented in manuscripts from around 5000 years ago in Indian, Chinese, Egyptian, Greek, Roman, and Syrian languages. The Rigveda, Atharvaveda, Charak Samitha, and Sushruta Samhita are some examples of classical Indian literature. Therefore, the traditional medicines and herbal remedies are drawn from rich traditions of ancient civilizations and scientific heritage.

Difference of herbal and conventional drugs (Philipson, 1990)

Although superficially similar, herbal medicine and conventional pharmacotherapy have three important differences:

Use of whole plants

Herbalists typically employ un purified plant extracts with a variety of components. These are said to interact synergistically such that the combined effect of the herb as a whole is higher than the sum of its individual effects. Additionally, it is asserted that using whole herbs as opposed to separated active components (or "buffering") reduces toxicity. Although the amounts of the constituent substances in two samples of a particular herbal drug may differ, practitioners assert that this generally does not result in clinical issues. There is some

experimental support for synergy and buffering in some whole plant preparations, but it is unknown to what extent this holds true for all herbal treatments.

Bioavailability of Herbal Drugs

Another factor of great significance is the herb's active ingredients' bioavailability. A substance must enter the bloodstream from the gastrointestinal tract before it may act systemically. Surprisingly little is known about herbal ingredients in this area⁹. After oral intake, compounds like barbering and hydrastine in the well-known botanical are essentially not absorbed. All animal studies demonstrating a systemic effect used parenteral treatment of these alkaloids. However, goldenseal continues to be one of the most popular herbs, is heavily advertised, and is recognised as a general immune stimulant by an uninformed audience.

Status of Herbal Medicine in India

As evidenced by Ayurveda, which could not have survived for two thousand years without a scientific foundation, India has a long heritage of herbal treatment. Atharvaveda is where Ayurveda, which is a Sanskrit term that literally translates as "knowledge of life," originated (Circa 1500-1000 BC).

The two most well-known Ayurvedic treatises are the Charak Samhita and the Sushruta Samhita. Several more, like Vagbhata's Ashtanghridaya (600), the Bela Samhita, the Kashyap Samhita, the Agnivesh Tantra, and the Madhava Nidan (700 AD), were compiled over the ages.

Uncontrolled observations in patients with liver disease seemingly gave similar result.

Double-blinded and well-designed clinical trials have also been conducted with Argyowardhani in viral hepatitis, *Mucuna pruriens* in Parkinson's disease. *Phyllanthus amarus* in hepatitis and *Tinospora cordifolia* in obstructive jaundice. India is one of the 12 mega biodiversity centres having over 45,000 plant species. About 1500 plants with medicinal uses are mentioned in ancient texts and around 800 plants have been used in traditional medicine. However, India has failed to make an impact in the global market with drugs derived from plants and the gap between India and other countries is widening rapidly in the herbal field. The export of herbal medicine from India is negligible despite the fact that the country has a rich traditional knowledge and heritage of herbal medicine.

The circumstance, which tends to frustrate a major developmental initiative for herbal products are many, sided in the country:

- i. There is no clear definition of the target to be achieved or a time frame within which the target, if any, should be achieved.
- ii. There is no co-ordination among the national laboratories that are investigating medicinal plants.
- iii. A serious dialogue between publicly funded institution and the industry is conspicuous by its absence.

A mechanism for regular interaction between the expert in Ayurveda and R&D group on medicinal plant does not exist. At the political level, Ayurveda is constantly extolled, but no effort is made to unify the scattered and thinly-spread effort into a powerful course of action with specified goal in the development of herbal drugs

Traditional herbal prescription with anti-RA effects

It is refreshing to state that many ancient traditional herbal prescriptions with anti-RA properties are currently used in this modern dispensation. The traditional herbal prescription is characterized by monarch, minister and assistant. Its advantage is mainly reflected in the emphasis on the combined treatment of multi-target, rather than the conventional treatment of single target.

Osteoporosis

The social impact of osteoporosis is enormous, and osteoporotic fractures are linked to high disease burden, healthcare costs, morbidity, and mortality (Hernlund *et al.*, 2013). Osteoporotic fractures, in particular hip fractures, cause impairment due to difficulties moving around and carrying out everyday activities, which is linked to an increase in nursing home and rehabilitation hospital admissions (Aizer 2014). When compared to the general population, men and women who have suffered hip or vertebral fragility fractures have higher death rates, particularly in the first year following the fracture. Osteoporosis is linked to a number of inflammatory diseases that rheumatologists treat, such as rheumatoid arthritis (RA), psoriatic arthritis, and ankylosing spondylitis (Maruottiet *al.*, 2014). Additionally, glucocorticoids, a medication used in rheumatology on a daily basis, a major risk factor for osteoporosis, are frequently prescribed.

Key Concepts in Understanding Bone Biology and the Treatment of Osteoporosis

In the process of remodelling bone, mineralized bone is resorbed by osteoclasts, then bone matrix is formed by osteoclasts, which is then mineralized. The adult skeleton's ability to sustain bone strength depends heavily on the process of bone remodelling. Osteoporosis develops when bone growth is outpaced by bone resorption due to ageing, low oestrogen levels, or other metabolic disturbances. Due to an increase in osteoclast number and activity, a decrease in osteoblast number and activity, or a combination of the two, bone resorption outpaces bone production. Antiresorptive medications for osteoporosis inhibit osteoclasts function, preventing bone resorption. Anabolic medications increase the rate of bone formation. Osteocyte, composing 90–95% of all bone cells in adult bone, also play an important role in regulating bone metabolism; they are the orchestrator of bone remodeling through regulation of both osteoclast and osteoblasts activity. Osteocyte act as mechanosensors, and they may help identify sites with micro damage and micro cracks for remodeling (Seeman *et al.*, 2006). Recent developments have improved our knowledge of bone biology. In osteoblasts, the Wnt signalling pathway is crucial for bone production. This pathway is activated by both parathyroid hormone (PTH) and bone morphogenic protein (BMP), which both have a bone anabolic effect. Sclerostin and Dickkopf WNT signalling pathway inhibitor 1 are its natural antagonists (DKK1). In reaction to mechanical stress and other metabolic changes, sclerostin is particularly produced in osteocyte and bone tissue (Rossini *et al.*, 2013).

In contrast, the receptor activator of nuclear factor- κ B (RANK) ligand (RANKL) pathway is significant in bone resorption. When osteoblasts release RANKL, it binds to RANK on osteoclasts. The proliferation, activation, and maturation of osteoclasts depend on this interaction. The skeleton is shielded from excessive resorption by osteoprotegerin (OPG), a decoy receptor for RANKL. OPG works to prevent RANKL from attaching to its receptor. Therefore, the RANKRANKL-OPG balance controls osteoclast-driven bone resorption.

Current medications for osteoporosis treatment

In line with advances in bone biology knowledge, the past several years have held major therapeutic advances in osteoporosis treatment. In adults at risk for fracture, osteoporosis treatment decreases fracture risk by approximately 70%. In patients with a prior hip fracture, secondary prevention has been shown to reduce both fracture risk and mortality. In Table 1.1; summarize the efficacy of these medications in preventing fractures.

Clinical scenarios	Therapeutic considerations	Rationale
Primary prevention, treatment of postmenopausal osteoporosis	Alendronate, risedronate, zoledronic acid, denosumab (proven antifracture efficacy)	Strong evidence for antifracture (spine, hip, nonvertebral) efficacy
Patient with osteoporosis and chronic kidney disease with eGFR of 15–30 ml/min	Denosumab	Denosumab is not renally cleared
Patient with osteoporosis with a high risk of hip fracture	Alendronate, risedronate, zoledronic acid, denosumab	These medications have been shown to decrease risk of hip fracture in randomized trials
Patient with multiple vertebral compression fractures	Consider teriparatide; bisphosphonates, raloxifene and denosumab also have efficacy to reduce vertebral fragility fractures	Teriparatide significantly reduces the risk of new vertebral fractures, multiple vertebral fractures and moderate to severe vertebral fractures
Patient with osteoporosis who has a prior history of oesophageal anomalies/dysmotility, gastric bypass surgery or GI intolerance to bisphosphonate therapy	Zoledronic acid, denosumab, teriparatide	Both zoledronic acid and denosumab are given parenterally; teriparatide does not have associated GI adverse effects
Patient at a risk for glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis	Alendronate, risedronate, zoledronic acid, consider teriparatide	Per American College of Rheumatology 2010 Recommendations for the Prevention and Treatment of Glucocorticoid-Induced Osteoporosis
Recently, postmenopausal woman with low BMD in spine who is at a high risk for breast cancer	Raloxifene	Raloxifene reduces the vertebral fragility fracture incidence and reduces the risk of invasive breast cancer
Older postmenopausal woman who has taken raloxifene for several years (BMD is stable, no incident fractures on treatment)	Consider switching to first-line agent for postmenopausal osteoporosis (alendronate, risedronate, zoledronic acid, denosumab)	Raloxifene not proven to decrease risk of hip fractures. Risk of hip fracture, risk of thromboembolism increases with age
Long dosing intervals are preferable (patients with poor compliance, nursing home patients with osteoporosis)	Zoledronic acid, denosumab, ibandronate, risedronate	See Table 1 for dosing intervals
Older postmenopausal woman with high fracture risk who has been on several years of oestrogen replacement therapy	Consider switching to first-line agent for postmenopausal osteoporosis (alendronate, risedronate, zoledronic acid, denosumab)	Oestrogen replacement therapy has been associated with an increased risk of coronary artery disease, pulmonary embolism and breast cancer in the Women's Health Initiative

Selective oestrogen receptor modulators

Selective oestrogen receptor modulators (SERMs) are a class of tissue-specific oestrogen receptor agonists and antagonists. In bone tissue, raloxifene exhibits oestrogen-specific agonist activity while in breast and endometrial tissue, it has selective antagonist activity. Raloxifene appears to not raise the risk of endometrial cancer while decreasing the chance of invasive breast cancer. Raloxifene has been reported to raise vertebral BMD by 2% to 3% and decrease the frequency of vertebral fractures by 35 to 43%, however it did not show any effectiveness in preventing hip fractures. SERMs should be taken into account in individuals with osteoporosis, especially for those who may be more susceptible to vertebral fractures and breast cancer (Mirkin & Pickar 2015). It's possible that less is being done to treat osteoporosis using SERMs.

Individualizing osteoporosis therapy

Specific clinical scenarios

Table 2 summarizes our approach to medication selection in unique clinical circumstances based on patient comorbidities and preference. There are cases that warrant comanagement with an endocrinologist or other metabolic bone disease specialist. One of the scenarios involves a patient with chronic kidney disease (CKD) because these patients may demonstrate low BMD due to other bone diseases such as CKD-metabolic bone disease, and vitamin D deficiency (Moe *et al.*, 2006).

Osteoporosis medications that decrease bone turnover are not warranted in patients with a dynamic bone disease, a form of CKD-metabolic bone disease. In patients with a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of 30–60 ml/min, screening for CKD-metabolic bone disease by measuring calcium, phosphate, 25-OH vitamin D and PTH levels is recommended. Another scenario in which comanagement is suggested is in the setting of mild elevated PTH and normal 25(OH) vitamin D level. Appropriate workup to determine the cause (primary, secondary or tertiary) of the PTH elevation should be performed. In cases of primary hyperparathyroidism, surgical evaluation is indicated when significant clinical manifestations occur (bone and muscle pain, hypercalciuria). In the presence of osteoporosis, surgical consultation may be indicated, yet clinical judgment is important particularly in cases where in the elevation of PTH is mild.

A typical Femoral Fractures and Osteonecrosis of the Jaw

Osteonecrosis of the jaw (ONJ) is defined as the presence of exposed and necrotic bone in the maxillofacial region that does not heal within 8 weeks. In patients undergoing invasive dental procedures (mainly tooth extractions), taking antiresorptive medications may increase the risk of ONJ. The highest risk of ONJ occurs in patients with malignancy-related skeletal conditions receiving high doses of intravenous bisphosphonates. The risk of ONJ is proportional to the duration and cumulative dose of antiresorptive agents (Suresh *et al.*, 2014).

Of note, a recent meta-analysis showed a 2.3-fold higher risk of ONJ in noncancerous patients also, but this complication was extremely rare with an estimated incidence of 0.02–0.06%. There may be an association of ONJ with bisphosphonates, albeit rare, but this risk is significantly outweighed by the potential benefit of fracture risk reduction.

Osteoporosis Medications on the Horizon

Numerous cutting-edge drugs with various modes of action are being developed to treat osteoporosis. The humanised monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) against sclerostin, romozumab, and blosozumab, have gained attention as new drugs in the previous year (Lewiecki, 2014). Sclerostin is an osteoblast action-inhibiting osteocyte, hence by inhibiting sclerostin, bone growth is encouraged.

BMD in the femoral neck, whole hip, and spine Interestingly, there was a correlation between the use of romosozumab and an increase in bone formation markers and a decrease in bone resorption markers, suggesting that the use of anti-sclerostin antibodies uncouples bone resorption and bone formation.

Goal-Directed Treatment of Osteoporosis

The BMD and fracture risk of a patient are the basis for current osteoporosis therapy strategies. The first-line treatments are typically oral bisphosphonates. Implementing a treatment plan was once viewed as a permanent intervention. The guideline is to take into account a drug holiday after 3-5 years of bisphosphonate treatment due to safety concerns, particularly with reference to bisphosphonates, ONJ, and AFF. When a patient is uncooperative or is viewed as a treatment failure, the usual course of treatment is changed (demonstrates a significant loss of BMD or sustains a fracture despite ongoing treatment). This management approach varies from other chronic conditions (hypertension and

hyperlipidemia), which are more goal-directed (measured using BMD, bone turnover indicators, or the occurrence of fractures), in that it is based on evidence of therapy response (Lewieckiet *al.*, 2013).

A defined treatment objective of a specific BMD or duration of time without a fracture has been recommended for goal-directed treatment of osteoporosis. Treatment objectives may be developed to allow doctors to increase therapy intensity if goals are not accomplished and to shorten the amount of time patients must endure therapy. This strategy benefits from current developments in osteoporosis drug research with various modes of action. A new paradigm may assist clinicians in managing osteoporosis more successfully while limiting adverse effects, despite the lack of clearly defined targets.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plants

Fresh leaves of *Drypetes Gossweileri* were collected from Botanical garden of Vindhya Herbals, Bhopal. The leaves were washed thoroughly with normal tap water followed by sterile distil water. Then leaves were dried under shaded condition at room temperature. Leaves were crushed to powder using grinding machine. Powder was stored at 4°C in tight air container bottle.

Phytochemical screening

The qualitative chemical experiments were carried out with some modifications for different extracts according to the methods mentioned in (Trease and Evans, 1978;Kokate, 1994):

1. Detection of alkaloids: Extracts dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered individually.

a) **Hager's Test:** Hager's reagent (saturated picric acid solution) was tested with filtrates. Alkaloids confirmed by precipitate formation in yellow colour.

2. Detection of carbohydrates: The extracts were separately dissolved and diluted in 5 ml of distilled water. For the existence of carbohydrates the filtrates were used to study.

a) **Fehling's Test:** Filtrates have been hydrolyzed with dil. HCl, alkali neutralized, and Fehling A&B solutions hot. Red precipitate development suggests the existence of reducing sugar.

3. Detection of glycosides: Extracts were hydrolysed with dil. HCl, and then subjected to test for glycosides.

a) **Keller-Killani test:** Extracts treated with 2ml glacial acetic acid containing a 2 drop of $FeCl_3$. A brown colour ring indicates the presences of cardiacglycosides.

4. Detection of saponins

a) **Froth Test:** Extracts were diluted with distilled water to 20ml and this was shaken in a graduated cylinder for 15 minutes. Pattern of 1 cm layer of foam indicates the incidence of saponins.

5. Detection of phenols

a) **Ferric Chloride Test:** Extracts were treated with 3-4 drops of a solution of ferric chloride. Bluish black color production suggests phenols are present.

6. Detection of Flavonoid

a) **Lead acetate Test:** Extracts is treated with a few drops of a solution of lead acetate. Precipitated yellow color production suggests the presence of Flavonoid.

7. Detection of proteins

a) **Xanthoproteic Test:** The extracts were treated with few drops of conc. Nitric acid. Formation of yellow colour indicates the presence of proteins.

8. Detection of diterpenes

a) **Copper acetate Test:** Extracts is dissolved in water and treated with 3-4 drops of a solution of copper acetate. Emerald green colouration suggests the existence of diterpenes.

***In vivo* anti-arthritis activity**

Animals

The animal studies were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC), constituted for the purpose of control and supervision of experimental animals by the Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India, New Delhi, India. In the present study, Wistar rats (150–200 g) were used. During 1 week of acclimatization (22 ± 1 °C temperature and 50– 80% humidity), with 12 h cycle variation between the light and dark, freely, animals consumed a standard diet for rodents and water filtered beforehand.

Acute toxicity study

The extract of *Drypetes Gossweleri* and *Drypetes Roxburghii* were assessed for acute oral toxicity using OECD ANNEX-423 standards (LD50). According to prior toxicity studies, *Drypetes gossweleri* and were delivered orally to rats (2000 mg/kg body weight).

Collagen-induced arthritic rats

It consisted of four groups (n=5) of Five animals each.

Group I: Control rats were administered with DMSO

Group II: Rats were administered with 0.1 mL of collagen into the right hind paw intradermally to induce arthritis

Group III: Collagen-induced arthritic rats treated with *Drypetesgossweleri*-100mg/kg/p.o. per day

Group IV: Collagen-induced arthritic rats treated with *Drypetesgossweleri*-200mg/kg/p.o. per day

Group VII: Arthritic rats induced with collagen were treated with Diclofenac Sodium (5 mg/kg per day)

On 1st day, excluding the control group, all the other groups of rats were given a single dose of 0.1 mL of collagen into the right hind footpad intradermally. The rats of III-VI groups were given *Drypetesgossweleri* and *Drypetesroxburghii* (100 and 200 mg/kg/p.o.) and rats of standard group were administered with diclofenac sodium (5 mg/kg per day) up to 28th days(Paval *et al.*, 2009).

Super Oxide dismutase

Principle

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) is an enzyme found in all living cells. An enzyme is a substance

that speeds up certain chemical reactions in the body. Superoxide dismutase helps break down potentially harmful oxygen molecules in cells. This might prevent damage to tissues. Free radicals are strongly associated with many pathological processes in the body. Due to this scavenging ability, SOD has garnered significant attention for therapeutic use. SOD is known to catalyze the dismutation of superoxide to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and O₂. SOD is present in most aerobic organisms and is assumed to play a central role in providing defense against oxidative stress. The chemical moiety of SOD contains some metal ions such as Cu⁺², Zn⁺², Mn⁺², and Fe⁺² in the active site, which influences and mediates the dismutation process. On the basis of these metallic cofactors, SOD can be classified into three distinct types viz, Cu/Zn-SOD, Mn-SOD, and Fe-SOD. The sensitivity of these three isozymes to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and potassium cyanide are different (Claiborne; 1985).

Procedure

The SOD activity was assayed by the method of Marklund and Marklund (1974). The total SOD assay volume (3.0 ml) consisted of 1.5 ml of 50 mM Tris- Cacodylate (Tris and Sodium cacodylate) buffer pH 8.2 (pH adjusted with 0.1 N HCl), 0.3 ml of nitro blue tetrazolium salt (NBT) (1 mM in water), 0.3 ml of Triton X- 100 (0.01%), 0.8 ml of water, 0.1 ml of sample and 0.01 ml of pyrogallol (60 mM in water). A blank was run simultaneously consisting of 0.1 ml water instead of 0.1 ml sample. Enzyme kinetic activity was recorded at 540 nm for three min and change in O.D/min (Δ O.D) was used to calculate % auto-oxidation inhibition to derive SOD units (U). One unit of SOD was defined as 50% inhibition of the auto-oxidation caused by a certain value of enzyme. The results of SOD activity have been expressed as U/mgprotein.

Calculation

$$\text{SOD} = \frac{C \times \text{Total Volume} \times 1000}{50 \times \text{Sample Volume} \times \text{mg Protein per ml}}$$

Unit: Units/ mg Protein

Lipid Peroxidation

Principle

Lipid peroxidation is the core reaction of ferroptosis, which is caused by the attack of oxidants on lipids. Due to the production of lipid peroxy radicals, hydroperoxides, and

various oxidation products, uncontrolled lipid peroxidation leads to membrane rupture and cell death. Lipid peroxidation can be determined quantitatively or qualitatively by a variety of methods. It can be measured by losses of fatty acids; amounts of primary peroxidation products; amounts of secondary products such as carbonyls and hydrocarbon gases; and reduction in antioxidant activity (Ohkawa *et al.*, 1979).

Procedure

The reaction mixture (1.0 ml) containing 0.1 M Phosphate buffer (pH 7.4; 0.58 ml), 100 mM ascorbic acid (Acid; 0.2 ml) and 100 mM Ferric chloride (FeCl_2 ; 0.02 ml) was incubated at 37°C for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was stopped by adding 10% TCA (0.1 ml). Following addition of 0.67% EDTA (1.0 ml), all the tubes were placed in boiling water bath at 90°C for 20 min and shifted to crushed ice-bath before centrifuging at 2500 rpm for 10 min. The amount of malonaldehyde (MDA) formed was assayed by measuring optical density of the supernatant at 532 nm. The result was expressed as nmol MDA formed / (min mg protein) at 37°C using molar extinction coefficient of $1.56 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Calculation

$$\text{LPO} = \frac{\text{Test O.D.} \times \text{Total Volume} \times 1}{1.56 \times 10^5 \times 10^{-9} \times \text{Sample Volume} \times \text{mg protein per ml}}$$

Unit: nmol MDA / min × mg protein

Estimation of reduced glutathione (GSH)

Principle

Glutathione is an antioxidant in plants, animals, fungi, and some bacteria and archaea. Glutathione is capable of preventing damage to important cellular components caused by reactive oxygen species such as free radicals, peroxides, lipid peroxides, and heavy metals. Glutathione synthesis, via expression of the rate-limiting enzyme glutamate-cysteine ligase is also a response to mitochondrial injury by such agents as acetaminophen. Glutathione in its reduced form (GSH) is a critical cofactor for several antioxidant pathways, including thiol-disulfide exchange reactions and glutathione peroxidase. Glutathione peroxidase has a higher affinity for hydrogen peroxide than does catalase, and it disposes of lipid peroxides, free radicals, and electrophilic drug metabolites. GSH is also a cofactor for conjugation reactions catalyzed by the glutathione S-transferases involved with phase 3 transport of drug metabolites into bile. Other reactions proceed nonenzymatically. In turn, the products include glutathione-protein mixed disulfides and oxidized glutathione. The latter can

be converted back to glutathione by proton donation catalyzed by glutathione reductase (Jollow *et al.*, 1974).

Procedure

Reduced GSH was assayed by the method of Jollow (Jollow *et al.*, 1974). Briefly, 1.0 mL of serum was precipitated with 1.0 mL of sulphosalicylic acid (4%). The samples were kept at 4 °C for at least 1 h and then subjected to centrifugation at 1200 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C. The assay mixture contained 0.1 mL supernatant, 2.7 mL phosphate buffer (0.1 mol/L, pH 7.4) and 0.2 mL 5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB or Ellman's reagent, 0.1 mmol/L, pH 8.0) in a total volume of 3.0 mL. The yellow colour developed was read immediately at 412 nm and the reduced GSH levels were expressed as percentage of control.

Statistical analysis

Variables of interest were entered and all data was analyzed using GraphPad Instant 3.06 software version 14 for windows XP (Microsoft Corporation). All statistical analysis is expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA, where applicable * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ was considered statistically significant, compared with vehicle.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extractive values of *Drypetesgossweileri*

Organoleptic evaluation and extractive values of *Drypetesgossweileri*.

Sr. No.	Extracts	Color	Taste/odor	Texture	% Yield (W/W)
1.	Chloroform	Blackish	Characteristics	Sticky	0.59
2.	Ethyl acetate	Dark green	Characteristics	Sticky	1.24
3.	Ethanollic	Dark green	Characteristics	Sticky	3.60
4.	Aqueous	Green	Characteristics	Solid powder	4.57

The organoleptic evaluation and extractive values examination is also done for an another plant specimen *Drypetesgossweileri*. Here, the lowest percentage yield of 0.59 is observed with chloroform extract with blackish colour and sticky texture. The ethyl acetate and ethanolic extract with dark green colour and same sticky texture resulted in percentage yield of 1.24% and 3.60 % respectively. The maximum percentage yield of 4.57% is accompanied by aqueous extract with solid powder like texture and green colour appearance. So, the capacity of various solvent for percentage yield can also be communicated as, Aqueous > Ethanolic > Ethyl acetate > chloroform. One can conclude that for the same aqueous extract the percentage yield of *Drypetesgossweileri* is twice greater than.

Result of phytochemical screening

Result of phytochemical screening of *Drypetesgossweileri*

S. No.	Constituents	Chloroform extract	Ethylacetate extract	Ethanolic extract	Aqueous extract
1.	Alkaloids Hager's Test:	-Ve	-Ve	-Ve	-Ve
2.	Cardiac Glycosides Keller-Killani test:	-Ve	-Ve	-Ve	-Ve
3.	Flavonoids Lead acetate Test: Alkaline test:	-Ve -Ve	+Ve -Ve	+Ve +Ve	-Ve +Ve
4.	Diterpenes Copper acetate Test:	-Ve	-Ve	+Ve	-Ve
5.	Phenol Ferric Chloride Test:	-Ve	-Ve	+Ve	-Ve
6.	Proteins Xanthoproteic Test:	-Ve	-Ve	+Ve	+Ve
7.	Carbohydrate Fehling's Test:	-Ve	-Ve	+Ve	-Ve
8.	Saponins Froth Test:	-Ve	-Ve	-Ve	+Ve
9.	Tannins Gelatin test:	-Ve	-Ve	-Ve	-Ve

+Ve = Positive, -Ve= Negative

In case of plant specimen *Drypetesgossweileri* the chloroform extract with lowest percentage yield also seen to have deprived of phytoconstituents as all phytochemical tests resulted in negative result. The ethyl acetate extracts only showed the presence of flavonoids. For ethanolic extract slightly better results are obtained as the ethanolic extract comprised with flavonoid, diterpene, phenol, proteins and carbohydrates. For the aqueous extract positive results are achieved with flavonoids, proteins and saponins.

Phytochemical screening of *Drypetesgossweileri*

Results of antioxidant activity using DPPH method

% Inhibition of ascorbic acid and ethanolic extract of *Drypetesgossweileri*

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Inhibition	
		Ascorbic acid	Ethanolic extract
1	10	41.5	10.55
2	20	47.7	19.24
3	40	52.9	25.84
4	60	67.4	34.77
5	80	75.8	41.22
6	100	89.6	45.95
IC 50		27.82	105.18

% Inhibition of ascorbic acid and ethanolic extract of *Drypetesgossweileri*

The antioxidant capacity of ethanolic extract of *Drypetesgossweileri* was also evaluated with the same DPPH method. Concentrations from 10 µg/ml to 100 µg/ml were prepared. The absorbance for each concentration was measured at wavelength of 517 nm. Further the IC₅₀ value were determined which revealed that for the standard ascorbic acid the IC₅₀ value was observed to be 27.82 while for the ethanolic extract of *Drypetesgossweileri* the IC₅₀ value assessed to be 105.18. So, by comparing the above results from two different plant specimens it can be interpreted that the Ethanolic extract of have more superior antioxidant activity than ethanolic extract of *Drypetesgossweileri*.

RESULTS OF ANTI-ARTHRITIS ACTIVITY

Acute Toxicity Study

Acute toxicity experiments in rats revealed that extract of *Drypetes Gossweileri* and was safe up to the maximum dosage of 2000 mg/kg b.wt. There was no morbidity or clinical presentation of symptoms throughout the 14-day acute toxicity phase. Accordingly, we chose to perform the main study using 100 and 200 mg/kg *Drypetes Gossweileri* based on the acute oral toxicity study data.

Collagen-Induced arthritis

Biochemical parameters

A dose of 100 and 200 mg/kg of *Drypetesgossweileri* (0.68±0.045; 0.81±0.033) and (0.77±0.043; 0.75±0.048), and 5 mg/kg of diclofenac sodium (0.79±0.039) treatment groups

paw volume was recover significantly ($p < 0.05$) as compared to control group up to 28 days, respectively.

Effect of *Drypetes Gossweileri* and *Drypetes Roxburghii* against Collagen-induced arthritis in rats

Paw volume (mL)					
Group	Drug and Dose	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
Group I	Normal Control (DMSO)	0.22±0.047	0.28±0.06	0.38±0.65	0.28±0.04
Group II	Collagen	0.77±0.021	0.88±0.055	0.99±0.054	0.81±0.049
Group III	Collagen + <i>Drypetesgossweileri</i> -100	0.68±0.045	0.80±0.047*	0.79±0.033*	0.67±0.039**
Group IV	Collagen + <i>Drypetesgossweileri</i> -200	0.81±0.033**	0.78±0.039**	0.76±0.039***	0.56±0.045***
Group V	Collagen + Diclofenac Sodium (5 mg/kg per day)	0.79±0.039	0.74±0.040**	0.66±0.048***	0.53±0.055***

Values are expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 5$). Values are statistically significant at *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$ (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The plant specimens namely *Drypetesgossweileri* were simultaneously analysed at various different parameters. In the initial stage of study organoleptic evaluation and determination of extractive values was carried out. The comparison was made between four different solvents namely chloroform, ethyl acetate, ethanol & water. The colour & texture of particular solvent extract was also taken into consideration. From the analysis it was revealed *Drypetesgossweileri* the aqueous solvent exhibited the highest percentage yields. *Drypetesgossweileri* aqueous extract with green colour & solid powder like texture found to have percentage yield of 4.57%. So, the percentage yields of *Drypetesgossweileri*. In case of phytochemical screening of The *Drypetesgossweileri* Ethanolic extract phytochemical test showed the presence of Flavonoid, diterpenes, phenol, proteins & carbohydrates. It can be interpreted that Ethanolic extract possess significant amount of phytoconstituents as compared to other type of extracts. As phytochemical screening already revealed the presence of flavonoid & phenol the quantitative estimation As phytochemical screening already revealed the presence of flavonoid & phenol the quantitative estimation plant *Drypetesgossweileri* the same pattern seems to be followed as the Ethanolic extract contain enhanced amount of total Phenol & total Flavonoid. The total phenol content was 0.48mg/100mg while total flavonoid content was 0.65mg/100mg. Since IC₅₀ and anti-radical

activity are inversely correlated, the lower the IC₅₀, the greater the antioxidant activity. Thus, quantity of phenol & flavonoid appears to be maximum in contrast with *Drypetes gossweileri*.

The anti oxidant activity was also checked for both the plant specimens. Numerous natural antioxidant enzymes, including glutathione peroxidase, catalase, and superoxide dismutase, can neutralise free radicals and hence preserve healthy cellular processes. However, it's possible that endogenous antioxidants won't be adequate to maintain ideal cellular activities under increased oxidative stress, necessitating the use of dietary antioxidants. Plant secondary metabolites that contain an aromatic ring with at least one hydroxyl group are known as phenolic and flavonoid compounds in nature. Due to the fact that their hydroxyl groups can directly support antioxidant action, phenolic compounds are effective electron donors.

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic, inflammatory joint disease that initially affects the joints, manifesting as pain, stiffness, and synovitis, leading to cartilage and bone erosion by invading fibrovascular tissue. The worldwide prevalence of RA is about 5 per 1000 adults. The disease affects women 2 to 3 times more often than men and occurs at any age. RA is characterized by infiltration of the synovial membrane in multiple joints with T cells, B cells, and monocytes. This process is preceded by the activation of endothelial cells; neovascularization (growth of new blood vessels) is another hallmark of RA synovitis. The expansion of synovial fibroblast-like and macrophage-like cells leads to a hyperplastic synovial lining layer. This expanded synovial membrane often termed "pannus," invades the particular bone at the cartilage-bone junction and leads to bony erosions and cartilage degradation. Molecules such as receptor activator of nuclear factor κ B ligand (RANKL), prostaglandins, and matrix metalloproteinase's are induced by pro-inflammatory cytokines, including tumour necrosis factor (TNF) and interleukin (IL)-6, and mediate signs and symptoms of the disease, including pain and swelling, and degradation of cartilage and bone.

Weather has been reported to have a major effect on arthritic pain, and various relationships between weather and arthritic pain intensity have been reported. So called "weather-sensitive pain" has been attributed to changes in barometric pressure, humidity, or temperature. Weather-sensitive pain in humans has been studied using only psychological factors, which could be affected by a range of confounders, such as emotional factors, individual variability, and different pain thresholds. RA, with symptoms such as swelling (joints), the release of RF (autoantibody), deformity (bone destruction), and systemic change, is a more frequent disease that presents major systemic clinically complications with a high mortality rate in patients

compared to healthy people. Recent studies have revealed that the pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), and interleukin-6 (IL-6) produced by T helper type-1 (Th1) cells have key role in pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis. It is also evident that the oxidative stress due to amelioration of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS and RNS) have significant role in the development and progression of rheumatoid arthritis and also in the age-dependent pathogenic processes of cancers, arteriosclerosis, neurodegenerative disorders and other diseased conditions.

Free radicals generated from macrophages, lymphocytes, neutrophils, and endothelial cells play important role in the pathophysiology of synovial inflammation. Thus, the degenerative changes in rheumatoid arthritis could be prevented by eliminating these oxidizing species along with the use of drugs with immunomodulatory activities, which will be of interest.

The current treatment therapy of rheumatoid arthritis such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs), TNF- α antagonist, anti-interleukin (IL-6) receptor antibodies, IL-1 receptor antagonist, steroidal agents and immunosuppressant/immunomodulators transiently suppress inflammation and ameliorate symptoms. However, they do not help significantly to treat the disease in the long term and may result in serious side effects including gastrointestinal disorders, immunodeficiency, and humoral disturbances. CFA-induced arthritis is a chronic inflammation characterized by two phases: An acute phase (from day 0) with local inflammatory reactions that give rise to primary arthritic lesions such as edema in the injected paw, followed by a chronic inflammatory phase (from day 15) with secondary arthritic lesions characterized by inflammatory edema in the controlateral paw. The first acute phase is caused by various mediators such as cytokines IL-1 β and TNF- α , prostaglandins, histamine, kinins and serotonin released by leukocytes that migrate to the affected region and are responsible for edema. The secondary chronic phase is a manifestation of cell-mediated autoimmunity and cytokine IL-6 is the principal mediator involved in the cartilage and bone degenerative process. Arthritis progression and anti-arthritic activity of drugs can be assessed through the measurement of several parameters such as volumes of both hind paws and arthritis score. Swelling of the injected hind paw (primary arthritic lesion) was used for evaluating the inflammatory response in the acute phase following CFA immunization while the increased volume of the controlateral hind paw (secondary arthritic lesion) was measured to estimate the generalized immune response leading to polyarthritis in the chronic phase. In the current

study, CFA-induced arthritis in rats was selected to induce arthritis model, because it is the best and most widely employed empirical model for arthritis with clinical and laboratory features such as chronic swelling in multiple joints due to accumulation of inflammatory cells, erosion of joint cartilage and bone destruction and it has close similarities to human rheumatoid diseases.

The genus *Drypetes* comprises approximately 160 species which has been used in the folk medicine of many cultures for many years in the treatment of various pathological conditions. Earlier phytochemical studies on some *Drypetes* plant species including *D. parrifolia*, *D. laciniata*, *D. inaequalis*, *D. armoracia*, *D. gossweileri*, *D. molunduana*, *D. roxburghii* have yielded flavonoids, chalcone glycosides, saponins, tripterpenoids, phenolics, alkaloids, etc.

Drypetessepiaria belongs to the family Putranjivaceae (Euphorbiaceae). It is an evergreen tree commonly grown in foothills and shrub jungles, and is widely distributed in Srilanka and some places of Tamil Nadu. It is locally known as Kalvirai (Tamil). This plant is used in folk medicine by the tribal people of Western Ghats to treat pain and inflammation. The seeds of this plant are used as a wild edible food by Palliyars (tribal Group) of Western Ghats, India.

In the current study, CIA-induced arthritis in rats was selected to induce arthritis model, because it is the best and most widely employed empirical model for arthritis with clinical and laboratory features such as chronic swelling in multiple joints due to accumulation of inflammatory cells, erosion of joint cartilage and bone destruction and it has close similarities to human rheumatoid diseases.

The present study shows that Rana Adhikary, *et al.*, Histopathological study of joints also supported the fact that *A. vasica* provided significant resistance against bone damage during chronic inflammatory reactions, the fact further supported by attenuation of SGPT, the clinical markers for arthritis (Adhikary *et al.*, 2016).

A dose of 100 and 200 mg/kg of *Drypetesgossweileri*(89.52±6.01; 77.53±2.42) (84.32±4.04; 67.33±6.15), and 5 mg/kg diclofenac sodium (57.73±3.58) treatment groups SGOT level was decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) as compared to control group, respectively.

The prescribed data represented by Rana Adhikary, *et al.* Administration of collagen II significantly increased levels of SGOT and SGPT, the markers of bone erosion. All three doses of AVE significantly reduced the SGOT and suggested an ability of the extract to

mitigate bone erosion at times of arthritic progression (Adhikary *et al.*, 2016).

From the results, it may be concluded that *Drypetesgossweileri* show a significant anti-arthritic effect may be due to the effect of antioxidants like flavonoids, phenols and saponins present in the plant. As a result of the present study, all of these biological activities have been found to be promising. These contributions can be used as parameters for the authentication of plants or for the development of newer drugs based on their activity. Several therapeutic advantages of an herbal drug are evident in the present study, and it is likely that it will be a potent anti-arthritis agent as well.

REFERENCES

1. Venkatesha, S.H., Dudics, S., Astry, B., Moudgil, K.D., Control of autoimmune inflammation by celastrol, a natural triterpenoid. *Pathog Dis.*, 2016; 74(6): 59.
2. Vetal, S., Bodhankar, S. L., Mohan, V., &Thakurdesai, P. A. Anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritic activity of type-A procyanidine polyphenols from bark of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* in rats. *Food Science and Human Wellness*, 2013; 2(2): 59-67.
3. Voundi, S. O., Nyegue, M., Lazar, I., Raducanu, D., Ndoeye, F. F., Stamate, M., & Etoa, F. X. Effect of essential oils on germination and growth of some pathogenic and spoilage spore-forming bacteria. *Foodborne Pathogens and Disease*, 2015; 12(6): 551-559.
4. Wang, F., Shi, L., Zhang, Y., Wang, K., Pei, F., Zhu, H., & Xue, Q. (2018). A traditional herbal formula Xianlinggubao for pain control and function improvement in patients with knee and hand osteoarthritis: a multicenter, randomized, open-label, controlled trial. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2018.
5. Wang, W., Sun, W., Jin, L., Caffeic acid alleviates inflammatory response in rheumatoid arthritis fibroblast-like synoviocytes by inhibiting phosphorylation of IkappaB kinase alpha/beta and IkappaBalpha. *Int. Immunopharm*, 2017a; 48: 61-66.
6. Wang, X., Zu, Y., Huang, L., Yu, J., Zhao, H., Wen, C., Chen, Z., Xu, Z., Treatment of rheumatoid arthritis with combination of methotrexate and *Tripterygium wilfordii*: a meta-analysis. *Life Sci.*, 2017b; 171: 45-50.
7. Wang, Y., Han, C.C., Cui, D., Li, Y., Ma, Y., Wei, W., Is macrophage polarization important in rheumatoid arthritis? *Int. Immunopharm*, 2017d; 50: 345-352.
8. Wansi, J. D., Wandji, J., Sewald, N., Nahar, L., Martin, C., & Sarker, S. D. Phytochemistry and pharmacology of the genus *Drypetes*: A review. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 2016; 190: 328-353.

9. Wehr, P., Purvis, H., Law, S.C., Thomas, R., Dendritic cells, T cells and their interaction in rheumatoid arthritis. *Clin. Exp. Immunol*, 2019; 196(1): 12–27.
10. Wendling, D., Prati, C., Chouk, M., & Verhoeven, F. Reactive arthritis: treatment challenges and future perspectives. *Current rheumatology reports*, 2020; 22(7): 1-7.
11. WHO, Regulatory situation of herbal medicines, Geneva, Switzerland. A worldwide review, 2016; 1-5.
12. Wollenhaupt, J., Lee, E. B., Curtis, J. R., Silverfield, J., Terry, K., Soma, K., & Cohen, S. Safety and efficacy of tofacitinib for up to 9.5 years in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis: final results of a global, open-label, long-term extension study. *Arthritis research & therapy*, 2019; 21(1): 1-18.
13. Xie, X., Li, H., Wang, Y., Wan, Z., Luo, S., Zhao, Z., Liu, J., Wu, X., Li, X., Li, X., Therapeutic effects of gentiopicroside on adjuvant-induced arthritis by inhibiting inflammation and oxidative stress in rats. *Int. Immunopharm*, 2019; 76: 105840.
14. Xu, C.Q., Qi, X.F., Wang, Y.J., Liang, Q.Q., Interpret of the exogenous evil of arthromyodynia in rheumatoid arthritis in the modern sense. *World Sci Tech.*, 2016; 18(11): 1883–1890.
15. Xu, L., Yu, Y., Sang, R., Li, J., Ge, B., Zhang, X., 2018a. Protective effects of taraxasterol against ethanol-induced liver injury by regulating CYP2E1/nrf2/HO-1 and NF-κB signaling pathways in mice. *Oxid Med Cell Longev* 8284107.
16. Xu, X. X., Bi, J. P., Ping, L., Li, P., & Li, F. A network pharmacology approach to determine the synergetic mechanisms of herb couple for treating rheumatic arthritis. *Drug design, development and therapy*, 2018; 12: 967.
17. Ya-Nan, H. E., Shui-Ping, O. U., Xiong, X., Yuan, P. A. N., Jin, P. E. I., Run-Chun, X. U., & Ming, Y. A. N. G. Stems and leaves of *Aconitum carmichaelii* Debx. as potential herbal resources for treating rheumatoid arthritis: chemical analysis, toxicity and activity evaluation. *Chinese journal of natural medicines*, 2018; 16(9): 644-652.
18. Yang, C.M., Chen, Y.W., Chi, P.L., Lin, C.C., Hsiao, L.D., Resveratrol inhibits BK-induced COX-2 transcription by suppressing acetylation of AP-1 and NF-kappaB in human rheumatoid arthritis synovial fibroblasts. *Biochem. Pharmacol*, 2017; 132: 77–91.
19. Yang, L., Sibbritt, D., & Adams, J. A critical review of complementary and alternative medicine use among people with arthritis: a focus upon prevalence, cost, user profiles, motivation, decision-making, perceived benefits and communication. *Rheumatology international*, 2017; 37(3): 337-351.

20. Yu, W.G., Shen, Y., Wu, J.Z., Gao, Y.B., Zhang, L.X., Madecassoside impedes invasion of rheumatoid fibroblast-like synoviocyte from adjuvant arthritis rats via inhibition of NF- κ B-mediated matrix metalloproteinase-13 expression. *Chin. J. Nat. Med.*, 2018; 16(5): 330–338.
21. Z.D. Zeng, Y.Z. Liang, F.T. Chau, S. Chen, D.K.W. Mok, C.O. Chan. Mass spectral profiling: An effective tool for quality control of herbal medicines, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2007; 604: 89-98.
22. Zhai, K.F., Duan, H., Chen, Y., Khan, G.J., Cao, W.G., Gao, G.Z., Shan, L.L., Wei, Z.J., Apoptosis effects of imperatorin on synoviocytes in rheumatoid arthritis through mitochondrial/caspase-mediated pathways. *Food Funct*, 2018; 9(4): 2070–2079.
23. Zhai, K.F., Duan, H., Cui, C.Y., Cao, Y.Y., Si, J.L., Yang, H.J., Wang, Y.C., Cao, W.G., Gao, G.Z., Wei, Z.J., Liquiritin from *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* attenuating rheumatoid arthritis via reducing inflammation, suppressing angiogenesis, and inhibiting MAPK signaling pathway. *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2019; 67(10): 2856–2864.
24. Zhai, K.F., Duan, H., Luo, L., Cao, W.G., Han, F.K., Shan, L.L., Fang, X.M., Protective effects of paeonol on inflammatory response in IL-1 β -induced human fibroblast-like synoviocytes and rheumatoid arthritis progression via modulating NF κ B pathway. *Inflammopharmacology*, 2017; 25: 523–532.
25. Zhang, C., Ma, K., Yang, Y., Wang, F., Li, W., Glaucocalyxin A suppresses inflammatory responses and induces apoptosis in TNF- α -induced human rheumatoid arthritis via modulation of the STAT3 pathway. *Chem. Biol. Interact*, 2021; 341: 109451.
26. Zhang, N., Zhang, Z. K., Yu, Y., Zhuo, Z., Zhang, G., & Zhang, B. T. Pros and cons of denosumab treatment for osteoporosis and implication for RANKL aptamer therapy. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 2020; 8: 325.
27. Zhang, P., Li, J., Han, Y., Wei Yu, X., Qin, L., Traditional Chinese medicine in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis: a general review. *Rheumatol. Int.*, 2010; 30(6): 713–718.
28. Zhao, S., Otieno, F., Akpan, A., & Moots, R. J. Complementary and alternative medicine use in rheumatoid arthritis: considerations for the pharmacological management of elderly patients. *Drugs & aging*, 2017; 34(4): 255-264.
29. Zheng, H., Feng, H., Zhang, W., Han, Y., & Zhao, W. Targeting autophagy by natural product Ursolic acid for prevention and treatment of osteoporosis. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 2020; 409: 115271.

30. Zhou, S., Huang, G., & Chen, G. Synthesis and biological activities of drugs for the treatment of osteoporosis. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2020; 197: 112313.
31. Zhu, N., & Hou, J. Exploring the mechanism of action Xianlingubao Prescription in the treatment of osteoporosis by network pharmacology. *Computational Biology and Chemistry*, 2020; 85: 107240.
32. Adhikary, R., A. Majhi, S. Mahanti, et al., Protective effects of methanolic extract of *Adhatoda vasica* Nees leaf in collagen-induced arthritis by modulation of synovial toll-like receptor-2 expression and release of pro-inflammatory mediators. *Journal of Nutrition & Intermediary Metabolism*, 2016; 3: 1-11.
33. Aletaha, D. and J. S. Smolen, Diagnosis and management of rheumatoid arthritis: a review. *Jama*, 2018; 320: 1360-1372.
34. Brand, D. D., K. A. Latham and E. F. Rosloniec, Collagen-induced arthritis. *Nature protocols*, 2007; 2: 1269-1275.
35. Campo, G. M., A. Avenoso, S. Campo, et al., Efficacy of treatment with glycosaminoglycans on experimental collagen-induced arthritis in rats. *Arthritis Res Ther.*, 2003; 5: 1-10.
36. Colpaert, F., T. Meert, P. De Witte, et al., Further evidence validating adjuvant arthritis as an experimental model of chronic pain in the rat. *Life sciences*, 1982; 31: 67-75.
37. Gadamsetty, G., S. Maru, A. Tyagi, et al., Anti-inflammatory, cytotoxic and antioxidant effects of methanolic extracts of *Drypetes sepriaria* (Euphorbiaceae). *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines*, 2013; 10: 274-282.
38. Koo, S. T., L. Chang-Hyung, H. Choi, et al., The effects of pressure on arthritic knees in a rat model of CFA-induced arthritis. *Pain Physician*, 2013; 16: E95.
39. Mahmood, N., N. Nasir, M. Rofiee, et al., *Muntingia calabura*: A review of its traditional uses, chemical properties, and pharmacological observations. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 2014; 52: 1598-1623.
40. Miyoshi, M. and S. Liu, Collagen-induced arthritis models. *Rheumatoid Arthritis*, Springer, 3-7.
41. Nasuti, C., D. Fedeli, L. Bordoni, et al., Anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritic and anti-nociceptive activities of *Nigella sativa* oil in a rat model of arthritis. *Antioxidants*, 2019; 8: 342.
42. Niino-Nanke, Y., H. Akama, M. Hara, et al., Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity in rheumatoid arthritis (RA): its clinical significance and synthesis of ALP in RA synovium. *Ryumachi.[Rheumatism]*, 1998; 38: 581-588.

43. Rhee, D. K., J. Marcelino, M. Baker, et al., The secreted glycoprotein lubricin protects cartilage surfaces and inhibits synovial cell overgrowth. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 2005; 115: 622-631.
44. Singh, S. and D. Majumdar, Effect of fixed oil of *Ocimum sanctum* against experimentally induced arthritis and joint edema in laboratory animals. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy*, 1996; 34: 218-222.
45. Suneela, D., P. Dipmala, H. Abhay, et al., Disease-modifying effect of anthraquinone prodrug with boswellic acid on collagenase-induced osteoarthritis in Wistar rats. *Inflammation & Allergy-Drug Targets (Formerly Current Drug Targets-Inflammation & Allergy)(Discontinued)*, 2013; 12: 288-295.
46. Umar, S., J. Zargan, K. Umar, et al., Modulation of the oxidative stress and inflammatory cytokine response by thymoquinone in the collagen induced arthritis in Wistar rats. *Chemico-biological interactions*, 2012; 197: 40-46.
47. Van der Heijde, D., Joint erosions and patients with early rheumatoid arthritis. *Rheumatology*, 1995; 34: 74-78.
48. Wang, W., H. Zhou and L. Liu, Side effects of methotrexate therapy for rheumatoid arthritis: a systematic review. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*, 2018; 158: 502-516.
49. Wang, X., X. Yan, F. Wang, et al., Role of methotrexate chronotherapy in collagen-induced rheumatoid arthritis in rats. *Zeitschrift für Rheumatologie*, 2018; 77: 249-255.